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Deep Learning Generative Models for Breast MRI Synthesis: A 3D-GAN Comparative Study

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Resumo

O cancro continua a contribuir significativamente para a mortalidade a nível mundial, sendo o cancro da mama uma constante preocupação, especialmente entre as mulheres. A deteção precoce desta doença melhora significativamente os resultados do tratamento, tornando imperativo melhorar os processos de diagnóstico. Assim, a ressonância magnética tornou-se uma ferramenta fundamental na imagem do cancro da mama, oferecendo precisão e independência da densidade mamária. No entanto, a dependência da interpretação da mesma por especialistas e os potenciais atrasos no diagnóstico representam desafios para esta técnica de imagem.

Desta forma, este trabalho aborda estes desafios utilizando aprendizagem computacional para auxiliar na deteção do cancro da mama. Sistemas tradicionais de diagnóstico assistido por computador, inspirados em mamografia e ressonância magnética, exigem *datasets* extensos e diversos para um treino eficaz. No entanto, a sua escassez, juntamente com a preservação da privacidade, requer abordagens inovadoras para a sua expansão. Assim, modelos generativos, incluindo modelos autoregressivos, *variational autoencoders*, *generative adversarial networks* e *diffusion models*, surgiram como ferramentas valiosas para gerar dados médicos sintéticos.

Motivado pela natureza tridimensional frequente das imagens médicas, este estudo explora a síntese de imagens 3D de alta resolução de MRI de mama utilizando modelos generativos avançados, nomeadamente: 3D WGAN-GP, 3D α -WGAN-GP e HA-GAN. Inicialmente, o modelo 3D α -WGAN-GP superou o 3D WGAN-GP na resolução de 64^3 com base em métricas FID, MMD e MS-SSIM. O modelo HA-GAN destacou-se na resolução de 128^3 , gerando imagens sem artefactos que ultrapassaram os modelos anteriores e obtendo valores de FID, MMD and MS-SSIM de 189.724, 200879.92 e 0.4136. Além disso, foi efetuado um teste visual com um profissional de saúde, onde o modelo obteve 71.67% de *accuracy*. Por fim, um modelo Real-ESRGAN, desenvolvido por um colega (Pedro Santos Pereira), aumentou a resolução das imagens geradas de 128^3 para 512^3 , o que melhorou ainda mais a clareza das imagens, crucial para diagnósticos médicos detalhados.

Abstract

Cancer remains a significant contributor to global mortality, with breast cancer emerging as a prevalent concern, particularly among women. Early detection significantly improves treatment outcomes, making it imperative to enhance diagnostic processes. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has become a pivotal tool in breast cancer imaging, offering precision and independence from breast density. However, the reliance on expert interpretation and potential delays in diagnosis pose challenges for this imaging technique.

This work addresses these challenges by using machine learning, to aid in breast cancer detection. Traditional computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems, inspired by mammography and MRI, require extensive and diverse datasets for effective training. Yet, the scarcity of such datasets, in addition to the preservation of privacy, needs innovative approaches for augmentation. Generative models, including autoregressive models, variational autoencoders (VAEs), generative adversarial networks (GANs) and diffusion models, have emerged as valuable tools for generating synthetic medical data.

Motivated by the, frequent, three-dimensional nature of medical images, this study explores the synthesis of high-resolution 3D breast MRI images using advanced generative models, such as: 3D WGAN-GP, 3D α -WGAN-GP and HA-GAN. Initially, 3D α -WGAN-GP outperformed 3D WGAN-GP at 64^3 resolution based on FID, MMD, and MS-SSIM metrics. HA-GAN excelled at 128^3 resolution, generating artifact-free images surpassing the previous models and obtaining FID, MMD, and MS-SSIM values of 189.724, 200879.92, and 0.4136, respectively. Additionally, a visual test was conducted with a healthcare professional, where the model achieved an accuracy of 71.67%. Finally, a Real-ESRGAN model, developed by a colleague (Pedro Santos Pereira), further enhanced image clarity, crucial for detailed medical diagnostics, by increasing the resolution of the images generated by HA-GAN from 128^3 to 512^3 .

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) from United Nations

This dissertation investigates the potential of generative models to synthesise breast MRI images, in order to help CAD systems to better detect and diagnose breast cancer.

In addition to its healthcare impact, the project contributes to broader sustainable development objectives outlined in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals¹ (SDGs). It aligns closely with goals related to good health and well-being (SDG 3), aiming to enhance healthcare infrastructure and technological innovation in medical imaging. Moreover, by promoting gender equality (SDG 5) through improved healthcare outcomes for women, the project ensures that all individuals have equal access to effective diagnostic services.

Through its innovative approach to medical imaging and AI-driven diagnostics, the project not only supports advancements in healthcare technology but also contributes to scientific research and development (SDG 9). By driving innovation in healthcare AI and medical imaging technology, the project strives to achieve sustainable improvements in diagnostic accuracy and patient care.

These SDGs are a global roadmap towards a more just and sustainable future, making this project an important step towards a fairer and more sustainable world. Table 1 presents a more detailed analysis on how this dissertation aligns with these goals, and how its impact can be measured.

¹<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Table 1: Contribution of the project to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with corresponding targets and performance indicators.

SDG	Target	Contribution	Performance indicators and metrics
3	3.4	This project aims to improve early detection and accurate diagnosis of breast cancer using advanced generative models to create high-quality 3D breast MRI images. Early and accurate diagnosis can significantly enhance the chances of successful treatment and survival, ultimately reducing breast cancer mortality rates.	Reduction in breast cancer mortality rates.
	3.8	By helping in developing more accurate and accessible diagnostic tools for breast cancer, this project may reduce the need for costly, invasive procedures and makes high-quality diagnostic services more widely available.	Accessibility and accuracy of breast cancer diagnostics
5	5.1	Breast cancer predominantly affects women. Improving breast cancer diagnostics directly contributes to better health outcomes for women, thereby promoting gender equality in healthcare. By ensuring that women receive timely and accurate diagnoses, the project supports equal health opportunities.	Improvement in women's health outcomes.
9	9.5	This project drives innovation in medical imaging by developing and utilizing generative models for creating 3D breast MRI images. It promotes advancements in medical technology and contributes to scientific research in the field of healthcare Artificial Intelligence (AI).	Reduction in breast cancer mortality rates

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Acronyms

ADNI	Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative
AE	Autoencoder
AE-GAN	Auto-encoding GAN
AFAB	Assigned Female At Birth
BiLSTM	Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory
CAD	Computer-Aided Diagnosis
CT	Computed Tomography
DCE	Dynamic Contrast Image
DCGAN	Deep-Convolutional GAN
DCIS	Ductal Carcinoma In Situ
DCNN	Deep Convolutional Neural Network
EMD	Earth Mover’s Distance
ELBO	Evidence Lower Bound
FID	Fréchet Inception Distance
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
HA-GAN	Hierarchical Amortized Generative Adversarial Network
IDC	Invasive Ductal Carcinoma
ILC	Invasive Lobular Carcinoma
IS	Inception Score
KL	Kullback-Leibler
LSGAN	Least Squares GAN
LSTM	Long Short Term Memory
MMD	Maximum Mean Discrepancy
MLP	Multi-layer Perceptron
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MS	Mode Score
MS-SSIM	Multi-Scale Structural Similarity
PGGAN	Progressive Growing GAN
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SPADEGAN	Spatially Adaptive Denormalization GAN
SSIM	Structural Similarity
WGAN	Wasserstein GAN
VAE	Variational Autoencoders
VQ-GAN	Vector Quantized GAN
VTT	Visual Turing Test

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context

Nowadays, cancer is one of the most common factors that lead to low life expectancy among humanity, being responsible for causing death in numerous countries in the world. In a more precise view, in women, breast cancer is one of the most predominant types of cancer and the second leading cause of death. In 2020, it surpassed lung cancer as the most diagnosed in the world, with 2.3 million new cases registered [1]. However, by detecting it in its early stages, the treatment rate becomes larger, increasing the survival rate. Because of this, the early detection of this type of disease is essential for the treatment process [2].

In addition to mammography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has been used to perform a more accurate and precise location of the tumor, becoming a well-established essential tool in breast imaging, since it presents high specificity, independence from breast density and, also, helps clinicians detect non-invasive breast cancer [2]. Despite this evolution, the process of detection using this imaging technique is very risky because it depends on the level of expertise of specialists, and it may lead to unnecessary biopsies and other assessments [3]. Besides this, it is a time-consuming task for specialists, which can create delays in diagnosis.

In recent years, the incorporation of techniques and methods of machine learning to detect breast cancer has been rapidly growing, intending to assist specialists, in improving their accuracy in breast cancer diagnosis, leading to more supported decision-making. These techniques are mainly inspired by computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems that support the diagnosis with conventional imaging techniques such as mammography and MRI [2]. Yet, these models, to have a high-level performance, need to be trained and this is only possible if the dataset, used in the training phase, is large and diverse. In other words, the cases that compose it need to cover as many situations as possible and should always aim to represent the real-world data distribution [4]. Since the breast is a highly deformable organ and can present various and unpredictable shapes while the patient is being scanned, for the CAD models to detect breast cancer, they need to be trained with high-quality datasets. If these conditions are stabilized, it is possible to prevent overfitting and make the models created more robust.

However, the acquisition of large quantities of data is not easy. Due to privacy and security reasons, these training datasets are scarce, which motivated researchers to develop methodologies to augment them. To do this, they appealed to generative models due to their ability to create new synthetic data, from already existing data.

Recently, distinct classes of generative models have been developed in the realm of image synthesis, which are autoregressive models, variational autoencoders (VAEs), generative adversarial networks (GANs), and diffusion models.

1.2 Motivation

Nowadays, medical images present, most of the time, a three-dimensional representation, which creates a spatially accurate representation of anatomical structures, capturing the width, height, and depth of these structures. However, most of the generative models, applied for data augmentation in the medical field, have been used to synthesize 2D images without extending their actions into the 3D representation, because images with voxels demand more computing resources when being directly applied to networks for 3D image synthesis. So, to tackle this challenge, certain models, designed for 3D image synthesis, adopt a strategy of generating the image through consecutive 2D slices, which subsequently are integrated to compose a 3D image. Despite this approach, a common drawback is the tendency for discontinuities between slices, with the inexistence of relationships between spatial characteristics [5].

1.3 Goals and Contributions

This study aims to implement and evaluate generative models capable of producing high-resolution 3D breast MRI scans assessing their performances using quantitative metrics and clinical evaluation. The models should generate synthetic samples that exhibit realistic and spatially coherent characteristics. Furthermore, these synthesized images should be convincingly realistic to the extent that they can deceive medical professionals. With this in mind, the contributions of this research are:

1. Assessment of the current limitations of 3D medical data synthesis;
2. Development of methodologies to generate artificial breast MRI data;
3. Evaluation of the methods implemented through the use of metrics and comparison with state-of-the-art approaches.

1.4 Structure

In terms of structure, besides this introduction, the document contains five more chapters. In Chapter 2 there is a comprehensive study of the anatomy of the breast, breast cancer, and the main

imaging techniques associated with this organ. Chapter 3 explores state-of-the-art generative models and their applications in 2D and 3D medical imaging. Also, it references the main evaluation metrics used to evaluate these models. In Chapter 4, there is a description of the datasets used in this work and the pre-processing methodology adopted to prepare the images used. Relatively to Chapter 5, this chapter references the implementation of the models studied in this project, as well as the main results, a Visual Turing Test (VTT) and the enhancement of the resolution of the images generated through a super-resolution model. Finally, Chapter 6 is responsible for transmitting the main conclusions of this dissertation, the main results that were obtained in this project and future work that can be implemented.

Chapter 2

Background

To develop models capable of creating new never-seen breast MRIs and to evaluate their level of realism, there has to be a good understanding of the main characteristics of the breasts in women. As such, in this chapter, the breast anatomy will be presented, followed by its respective cancer. Finally, it is reviewed how MRI images are produced and some advantages of their use in the comprehensive assessment and management of breast cancer.

2.1 Breast Anatomy

Women's breasts are a complex and unique anatomical structure essential in the female reproductive system. These are a pair of mammary glands that grow from the front of the chest in teen and adult females. Also, the breast assumes a teardrop shape, positioned from the second to the sixth rib in the front of the human rib cage.

For people who were assigned female at birth (AFAB), three different types of tissues compose the breast and it is during puberty, where it can be observed the major growth of these different tissues [6].

Glandular tissue includes the lobes which are composed of the lobules (15 to 20 smaller sacs that can produce milk) which are arranged inside the lobes in clusters. Besides these glands, there are ducts, which are thin tubes that are connected to the nipple. Breast cancer is originated, most of the time, in these areas of glandular tissue.

Another type of tissue present in a single breast is the connective tissue, which is the same that ligaments are made of. Its main purpose is to be a holding structure for the glandular and fatty breast tissues.

Finally, there is adipose tissue, which is a collection of fat cells that fills in the areas between glandular and connective tissue, extending from the collarbone to the armpit and across the ribcage. As a woman gets older, especially after menopause, there is an increase in the quantity of adipose. Also, it is responsible for determining the breast size of a woman. However, there is an important difference between the size of the breasts and their density.

Dense breast is a term used to characterize women who have breasts with large quantities of glandular and connective tissues, while there are fewer quantities of fatty tissue. This characteristic is normal in women, however it can be a disadvantage. Women with higher-density breasts have higher risks of having breast cancer [7]. Besides, while performing exams, such as mammography, dense breast tissue and tumors are difficult to differentiate, since both appear in white. That is why, most of the time, specialists recommend high-density breast women to perform an MRI, which might detect tumors that were undetectable in a mammography exam, since it is a more sensitive method [8].

In Figure 2.1, a representation of the main components of a woman's breast is presented.

Figure 2.1: Women breast anatomy, from [6].

2.2 Breast Cancer

At its fundamental level, cancer is a disease affecting the genes within human body cells, which play a pivotal role in regulating their functioning. These alterations to these genes can lead to malfunctions, prompting cells to inappropriately grow and divide or inhibiting their natural process of cell death. As a consequence, these irregular cells have the potential to develop masses that are called tumors, which can be classified as benign or malignant [9].

Benign tumors are slow-growing, well-encapsulated masses of cells that stay localized and do not invade nearby tissues or spread. They are generally not life-threatening, since they mostly do not present symptoms, and can often be surgically removed if they grow large. On the other hand, malignant tumors, also known as cancer, consist of rapidly and uncontrollably dividing of cells.

They are invasive, can infiltrate nearby tissues, and have the potential to metastasize to other parts of the body, posing a greater threat to human health [10].

Relatively to breast cancer, this is a type of cancer that can start on only one or both breasts and both men and women can have this disease. Nonetheless, it happens more prominently in women, with 99% of the cases, whereas in men occur 0.5 to 1% of the times [11].

The majority of breast cancers fall under the category of carcinomas, which are tumors that originate from epithelial cells lining organs and tissues throughout the body. When a carcinoma is formed in the breast it is named adenocarcinoma, since its origin is in cells from the ducts or the lobules [12]. The most common types of adenocarcinoma are ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) and invasive carcinoma.

DCIS (see Figure 2.2) is a non-invasive type of breast cancer that refers to a stage where the cells lining the ducts change into cancer cells but have not yet spread into other breast tissues [13]. This type of breast cancer is a very early cancer, where almost all women with this disease are treated. However, if it is left untreated or undetected, it may spread into the surrounding breast tissue, becoming an invasive cancer.

Figure 2.2: MRI breast image revealing DCIS inside the circle represented, from [14].

In the invasive carcinoma category, there are mainly two types, which are invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) and invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC) [15].

Regarding the first one (see Figure 2.3), this type of invasive breast cancer is one of the most common types and it starts in the cells that compose the milk duct in the breast. From there, the cancer goes beyond the duct and grows into the nearby breast tissues [15].

Relatively to the second type, ILC initiates in the milk-producing glands (lobules) of the breast and similarly to IDC, it has the potential to metastasize to other parts of the body. Detecting invasive lobular carcinoma through physical examinations and imaging, such as mammograms, may pose greater challenges compared to invasive ductal carcinoma. Furthermore, ILC is more

Figure 2.3: MRI breast image revealing IDC pointed by the green arrow, from [16].

inclined to affect both breasts when contrasted with other forms of invasive carcinoma, being the second type of breast cancer most common to appear in women [15].

Breast cancer symptoms, particularly in advanced stages, can manifest as many combinations. In the early stages, many individuals may not experience noticeable symptoms. However, some examples of are painless breast lump or thickening, modifications in the breast and the skin, changes in the appearance of the nipple or the surrounding skin (areola) and bloody discharge from the nipple [11].

In terms of treatment of breast cancer, it depends on the contingent extent of the spread, whether to lymph nodes or other parts of the body. To diminish the risk of recurrence, doctors employ a combination of treatments, such as surgical removal of the breast tumor, radiation therapy and medications aimed at eliminating cancer cells and preventing their dissemination. This may involve hormonal therapies, chemotherapy, or targeted biological therapies [11]. Naturally, these treatments are more tolerated if performed in the early stages of the disease.

2.3 Breast Imaging

The early and accurate diagnosis plays a pivotal role in saving lives from breast cancer. Recent years have witnessed remarkable progress in diagnostic imaging for breast health, with mammography emerging as the most widely utilized diagnostic test, globally.

Mammography, using low-dose X-ray technology, serves as a crucial method for imaging the breast and detecting abnormalities associated with breast cancer, and it has long been a cornerstone in breast cancer screening. This imaging method has proven instrumental in identifying abnormalities, such as masses or microcalcifications, that may indicate the presence of breast cancer. It, still, remains a widely utilized tool for routine screening due to its effectiveness in detecting early-stage breast cancer [17]. However, this technique raised many doubts among researchers and specialists, because, the benefit of doing this type of imaging was not enough to compensate for

the risk of, potentially, spreading the cancer in some age groups, due to the radiation. Also, mammography was not reliably performed in women with dense breast tissue, showing low sensitivity, in some cases [18]. In response to these challenges, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) emerged as a complementary and sometimes more sensitive imaging technique for breast cancer detection.

Breast MRI uses strong magnets to make images of soft tissue parts from various angles, being able to create 2D images, represented in Figure 2.5, that can be stacked to produce a 3D image. To capture these images, the patient will lie face down on a table, that will slide into a long tube, with their arms above the head and the breasts hung down into an opening so they can be decompressed, to facilitate the scanning process (see Figure 2.4). While inside, the technologist responsible for the scan will take sets of images that can last 30 to 45 minutes [19].

Figure 2.4: Representation of MRI scanning process, from [19].

Figure 2.5: Breast MRI slice with irregular mass (arrow), from [18].

However, one of the main disadvantages of MRI is the fact that sometimes can lead clinicians to diagnose false-positive cases [18], by finding other lesions that do not relate to cancer. Besides, MRI can have a higher cost for the patient when compared to other medical imaging techniques.

2.4 Summary

The female breast is a complex structure consisting of glandular, connective, and adipose tissues, that needs to be understood in detail, to create models to generate synthetic images that will help in the early diagnosis of breast cancer. In terms of breast imaging, mammography is a widely used screening tool for breast cancer, but its limitations include radiation risks and reduced sensitivity in dense breasts. Because of this, MRI has emerged as a complementary and more sensitive imaging technique, which uses strong magnets to create 2D and 3D images of breast tissue, aiding in the detection of abnormalities. However, MRI presents disadvantages, as it may lead to false-positive cases and can be more expensive than other imaging methods.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

In recent years, due to their vast spectrum of possible applications such as image synthesis (e.g., super-resolution, text-to-image, and image-to-image conversion), audio synthesis (e.g., speech and music), reinforcement learning, and more, deep generative models have witnessed a large increase in its study, which simultaneously took the understanding of unsupervised learning a step further. Fundamentally, they can acquire the main characteristics from a distribution of a particular dataset to, then, generate new and different samples from the dataset in question [20].

In this section, we focus our analysis on different types of generative models: autoregressive models, VAEs, GANs and diffusion models, to build basic and essential knowledge for the work planned to be done in a posterior phase. The models presented in this section are applied mostly to 2D images, however, they can be used in 3D scenarios through adjustments in their frameworks.

3.1 Autoregressive models

In the context of generative models, autoregressive models operate on pixel-level data. They generate images one pixel at a time, conditioning each pixel's probability distribution on the previously generated pixels. The idea is to capture the dependencies and structure within the image data by considering the sequential relationships between pixels. By doing this, it can predict the value of the next pixel, given all the previous pixel values that it knows of [21]. However, one of the main disadvantages of this type of model is its slow sampling in large images, since it is necessary to go through the whole image to use this model and generate new samples.

These models [22] are based on the chain rule of probability, where a variable can be decomposed as $x = x_1, \dots, x_n$. Because of this, the probability of this variable can be written as it is represented in Equation 3.1, which expresses the joint probability $P(x)$ of the entire sequence as the product of conditional probabilities of each individual element x_i given all preceding elements x_1, \dots, x_{i-1} .

$$P(x) = P(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i | x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}) \quad (3.1)$$

In [21], Kalchbrenner et al. used a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), which has a good performance in a vast number of sequence problems, such as handwriting generation, character prediction, and machine translation. As it is considered an autoregressive model, its primary objective is to generate images pixel by pixel, assigning a probability $p(x)$ to each image x formed of $n \times n$ pixels (see Equation 3.2).

$$P(x) = \prod_{i=1}^{n^2} p(x_i | x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}) \quad (3.2)$$

Through the previous equation, the probability for the i -th pixel is calculated having into account all previous pixels as well as each of the color channels, Red, Green and Blue (RGB), which is represented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Generation of pixel x_i from the previous pixels, from [21].

For the study in question, two different architectures were used to define the ordering of the previous pixels. These are composed by, on one hand, Row LSTM layers, and, on the other hand, by Diagonal Bidirectional LSTM. The Row LSTM operates by sequentially processing each row of the image from top to bottom, extracting features for the entire row simultaneously. It effectively captures information within a triangular region above each pixel, however, it cannot capture the entirety of the available region. The Diagonal BiLSTM uses the entire available region, since the processing goes on diagonally and it can move in both directions. Figure 3.2 represents the different processes between the layers mentioned previously.

In terms of results from this study, the architecture using Diagonal BiLSTM layers performed better, demonstrating better scalability when working with larger datasets.

3.2 Variational Autoencoders

An Autoencoder (AE) is a neural network composed of two modules: the encoder and decoder, with the main purpose of recreating its input [23]. The encoder has the objective of continually reduce the dimensionality (reducing the number of features that describe the data) to a smaller hidden layer, called the code, also known as latent space. In a similar and inverted process, the

Figure 3.2: Differences between Row LSTM (left) and Diagonal BiLSTM (right) layers, from [23].

decoder recreates the same input structure from the code layer. The standard architecture of an AE is represented in Figure 3.3.

Despite this, the goal of an AE, as a generative model, is not to create perfect copies of the dataset used during training but to create new and never-before-seen examples. However, this does not happen because the AE is optimized to generate samples with zero loss in the process, leading to situations of overfitting without ever knowing the ground truth distribution of the training data.

Figure 3.3: Standard Architecture of an Autoencoder, from [23].

To address this problem, it was established a new type of this model, which is one of the most used, nowadays, to generate data, called variational autoencoder (VAE).

The VAE [24] is a type of AE that tries to learn the distribution of the code layer. The encoder generates a probability distribution over the latent space created and then, the decoder samples from this distribution to generate a new data point. This architecture, which is represented in Figure 3.4, is trained to minimize the difference between the data encoded and subsequently decoded and the original input data.

Figure 3.4: Standard Architecture of a VAE, from [23].

The training process of this generative model begins with encoding the input into a distribution within the latent space. Next, a sample is drawn from this distribution, which is then decoded to produce an output. The error between the generated output and the target is calculated and subsequently backpropagated through the network to update the model parameters.

To be more precise, the variable x represents the original data, which is generated from a latent variable z , the encoded representation. Accordingly, the decoder is defined by $p(x|z)$, that represents the distribution of the decoded variable given the encoded one. Conversely, the encoder is represented by $p(z|x)$, illustrating the distribution of the encoded variable given the decoded one, as shown in Equation 3.3.

$$p(z|x) = \frac{p(x|z)p(z)}{p(x)} = \frac{p(x|z)p(z)}{\int p(x|z)p(z) dz} \quad (3.3)$$

In this context, it is possible to use Bayes' theorem to compute $p(z|x)$. However, because of denominator, this computation is intractable and it requires the use of variational inference, where the value of $p(z|x)$ is an approximate value using another distribution $q(z|x)$ that is similar to a normal distribution, represented in Figure 3.4. For this, it is used the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence to evaluate the difference between both distributions, to minimize it, represented in Equation 3.4.

$$\min KL(q(z|x) || p(z|x)) = E_q[\log q(z|x)] - E_q[\log p(x,z)] + \log p(x) \quad (3.4)$$

Since the term $\log p(x)$ is a constant, it can be omitted. Because of this, the Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO) function can be used, as it is explained in Equation 3.5:

$$ELBO = E_q[\log q(z,x)] - E[\log q(x|z)] \quad (3.5)$$

The reconstruction loss is, then, added to the ELBO function, creating the loss function that characterizes this type of generative model, represented by Equation 3.6.

$$\min L(x, x') + ELBO \quad (3.6)$$

In [24], the VAE models developed were tested with the MNIST dataset, which is a database of various handwritten numbers. The results (see Figure 3.5) were positive because the models were able to generate trustworthy images of the given dataset. However, these were, still, characterized by a certain level of blurriness, which is the main drawback of VAEs.

Figure 3.5: Samples generated by VAEs, from MNIST dataset, for different dimensions of the used latent space, from [24].

3.3 Generative Adversarial Networks

GAN [25] is a type of deep generative model, where its framework, represented in Figure 3.6, is based on an adversarial process in which two entities compete against each other. One is called the generator and its main purpose is to generate samples that can be easily perceived as one from a certain dataset. The other is the discriminator, which tries to guess if the sample generated by the generator belongs to the dataset in question or not. Both the generator and the discriminator play a min-max game, where $D(x)$ is the probability that a given sample belongs to a certain dataset. As represented in Equation 3.7, the discriminator will try to maximize the assignment of the correct label to the samples that is classifying. On the other hand, the generator will try to minimize $\log(1 - D(G(z)))$, which is the probability that a sample generated from G does not belong to the dataset.

Both models train to improve their performances in this adversarial process, until the moment when the samples generated become so similar to the true data that it becomes indistinguishable for the discriminator.

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = E_{x \sim p_{data}(x)} [\log D(x)] + E_{z \sim p_z(z)} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.6: Standard architecture of a GAN, from [26].

GANs can be extremely difficult to train, since two networks are competing against each other and proceeding with their training concurrently, which can, most of the time, create scenarios where the searched equilibrium is not reached [26]. This creates the main disadvantage of using GANs for generating synthetic images, despite synthesizing high-quality samples.

3.3.1 Deep Convolutional GAN

The Deep Convolutional GAN (DCGAN) was first introduced in [27] and it is based on the standard architecture presented, previously. However, to generate higher-quality synthetic images, this type of GAN uses deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) instead of multi-layer perceptron networks (MLP), which were used in the architecture from Figure 3.6. Despite this fundamental change, some modifications to these convolutional layers were done, to create a more stable environment for DCGAN to train. These were:

- Replace all max pooling layers with strided convolutions;
- For upsampling, utilize transposed convolution;
- Perform batch normalization;
- Use Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) as the activation function in the generator, but not in the output of this block (hyperbolic tangent);
- Use LeakyReLU for the activation function of the discriminator.

One interesting aspect approached in [27] was the ability to control the generator in a process called Latent Space Interpolation. Through the use of simple arithmetic operations in the latent space, like the example vector("King") - vector("Man") + vector("Woman") results in vector("Queen"), Radford et al. were able to explore this characteristic in their generated images, with the respective results represented in Figure 3.9. However, with this technique, it is not possible to perform detailed modifications to the images generated, because the latent space is entangled.

Figure 3.7: Latent Space Interpolation Results of DCGAN, from [27].

3.3.2 Wasserstein GAN

The Wasserstein GAN (WGAN) is an extension to the DCGAN architecture and was first introduced in 2017, by Arjovsky et al. [28]. This model was created to reduce the instability in the training process and the condition of mode collapse, where the generator creates a reduced number of samples derived from the distribution of the input images.

In order for WGAN to address these problems, it uses the Wasserstein distance, or Earth Mover's Distance (EMD), to measure the difference between real and generated data distributions. Formally, it is defined by Equation 3.8.

$$W(P_r, P_g) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Pi(P_r, P_g)} E_{(x,y) \sim \gamma} [\|x - y\|] \quad (3.8)$$

In this equation, $\Pi(P_r, P_g)$ represents the set of all joint distributions $\gamma(x,y)$ in which the marginals are P_r and P_g . The authors proposed the Kantorovich-Rubinstein duality which is a practical way to compute the Wasserstein distance. This expression is represented in Equation 3.9.

$$W(P_r, P_g) = \sup_{\|f\|_{L^1} \leq 1} E_{x \sim P_r} [f(x)] - E_{x \sim P_g} [f(x)] \quad (3.9)$$

In WGAN, the discriminator is replaced by a critic f , which scores the realness of samples instead of classifying them as real or fake. It aims to maximize the difference in scores between real and generated samples, while the generator aims to minimize it.

WGAN originally used weight clipping, which involves clipping the weights of the critic to a small fixed range (e.g., $[-0.01, 0.01]$). However, it still can suffer from unstable training and slow convergence. Because of this, an improved version of WGAN, called WGAN-GP [29], replaces weight clipping with a gradient penalty. The gradient penalty is defined as it is represented in Equation 3.10, where \hat{x} is sampled uniformly along straight lines between pairs of points from the real and generated data distributions, and λ is a penalty coefficient.

$$\mathcal{L}_{GP} = \lambda E_{\hat{x} \sim P_{\hat{x}}} [(\|\nabla_{\hat{x}} f(\hat{x})\|_2 - 1)^2] \quad (3.10)$$

3.3.3 StyleGAN

StyleGAN [30], created by NVIDIA¹, brings significant advancements in improving both the quality and control of generated images. This cutting-edge architecture addresses many of the issues related to latent space entanglement that were previously encountered in image generation using DCGAN.

Like its predecessor, the Progressive Growing GAN (PGGAN) [31], it uses a progressive growing technique. This approach allowed for the synthesis of extremely large, high-quality images by progressively growing both the discriminator and generator models, during the training process (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8: PGGAN training process, from [30]. As the training advances, layers are introduced to the generator and the discriminator.

The only difference to the previous type of GAN is the generator architecture. In StyleGAN, it is introduced a mapping network that transforms the latent vector into an intermediate latent space W . This mapping allows for better disentanglement of different factors of variation, making it easier to control specific features of generated images.

¹NVIDIA can be found at: <https://www.nvidia.com/>

Figure 3.9: Architecture of the generator from a PGGAN (left) and a StyleGAN (right), from [30].

One notable feature of StyleGAN is the ability to control specific visual aspects independently. Through manipulation of the intermediate latent space \mathcal{W} , users can blend styles to create hybrid images, by combining the pose of one face with the facial features of another, known as mixing regularization. During training, a specified percentage of images are generated using two random latent codes instead of one. In this process, the synthesis network facilitates a transition between these codes at a randomly chosen point and, specifically, both latent codes z_1 and z_2 are passed through the mapping network, resulting in corresponding w_1 and w_2 values that control the image generation. In the StyleGAN framework [30], w_1 influences the image generation before the crossover point, while w_2 affects it after. Detailed results demonstrating this capability are shown in Figure A.1 in Appendix A.

3.4 Diffusion Models

Diffusion models [32] are a type of generative model, where the data generation process is characterized by the iterative application of a forward diffusion process, where controlled noise is incrementally added to the samples, and by a reverse diffusion process, where the model tries to learn how to recover the original data from the noise added, creating new images. A simple representation of a diffusion model is illustrated in Figure 3.10.

Relatively to the forward process [33], it is a Markov chain (see Equation 3.11) of T diffusion steps, where Gaussian noise is gradually added to the original data. In other words, it starts by sampling a data point x_0 from the real data distribution $q(x)$, $x_0 \sim q(x)$, and then it adds a certain quantity of Gaussian noise with variance β_t to x_{t-1} , creating a new variable x_t with distribution $q(x_t|x_{t-1})$ (see Equation 3.12).

Figure 3.10: Representation of a diffusion model, from [33].

$$q(x_{1:T}|x_0) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(x_t|x_{t-1}), \quad (3.11)$$

$$q(x_t|x_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(x_t; (1 - \beta_t)x_{t-1}, \beta_t I), \quad (3.12)$$

Besides, the forward process presents an important feature, which enables the process of sampling x_t of timestamp t without the need to go through the forward process again. This property is achieved by using the notation $\alpha_t := 1 - \beta_t$ and $\bar{\alpha}_t := \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$. These expressions lead to Equations 3.13 and 3.14:

$$q(x_t|x_0) = \mathcal{N}(x_t; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}x_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)I) \quad (3.13)$$

$$q(x_t|x_0) = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}x_0 + \varepsilon\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}, \quad \varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I) \quad (3.14)$$

In contrast, the reverse diffusion process [33] is the process of learning to recover the original data by reversing the noising process applied in the forward process. To do this, it is used a trained neural network, usually, a U-Net, represented by p_θ , to predict the mean μ_θ and diagonal covariance matrix Σ_θ , represented in Equation 3.15.

$$p_\theta(x_{t-1}|x_t) := \mathcal{N}(x_{t-1}; \mu_\theta(x_t, t), \Sigma_\theta(x_t, t)) \quad (3.15)$$

However, the authors from [33] decided not to directly parameterize μ_θ , but parameterize $\varepsilon_\theta(x_t, t)$, that predicts the noise of a sample created by the forward process in a timestamp t . While training the model, it is possible to know the timestep t and the noise ε applied to an image in the forward process. This creates the objective of minimizing the mean-squared error loss between the true and predicted noise (see Equation 3.16).

$$L_{simple} = E_{t \sim [1, T], x_0 \sim q(x_0), \varepsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)} [\|\varepsilon - \varepsilon_\theta(x_t, t)\|^2] \quad (3.16)$$

In terms of image generation, diffusion models are, currently, the best among generative models, even surpassing GANs, which are considered the state-of-the-art approach in this field [34]. In this study [34], it was compared the performance of a famous type of GAN, BigGAN-deep, with a

diffusion model, by using the Frechet Inception Distance (FID) evaluation metric (see Section 3.5). The images generated by each model are represented in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11: Samples generated by BigGAN-deep model (left), diffusion model (middle) and from training set (right), from [34].

The GAN model obtained a FID value of 6.95, while the diffusion model obtained 4.59. Taking into consideration how the FID metric works (Section 3.5.3), it can be concluded that the diffusion model produced higher-quality, since its value is lower than the one presented by the GAN model. However, it must be taken into account that, even though these models present very promising results, their training is computationally expensive, because of the usage of denoising and noising steps.

3.5 Objective Metrics in Generative Models

Assessing the performance of generative models is a crucial aspect in understanding their capabilities, but also their limitations. As they continue to evolve, the need for robust and comprehensive evaluation metrics becomes increasingly imperative.

The evaluation of generative models extends beyond traditional quantitative measures, encompassing aspects such as fidelity, diversity, and real-world applicability. Quantitative metrics provide objective measures, allowing for systematic comparisons, while qualitative evaluations by human assessors offer valuable insights into the perceptual quality and relevance of generated samples.

This section approaches various metrics, from quantitative to qualitative, created to evaluate the efficacy of the most used generative models.

3.5.1 Inception Score

The Inception Score (IS) [35] is based on the Inception Model [36] which was used to create a new metric that is able to evaluate the performance of generative models, more precisely GANs. Each generated image is analyzed, obtaining the conditional label distribution $p(y | x)$. In the context of meaningful objects, images are expected to exhibit a low-entropy conditional label

distribution, whereas, to ensure the generation of diverse images, we anticipate a high-entropy marginal distribution, $\int p(y | x = G(z)) dz$.

Encapsulating these requirements, it was proposed the metric represented in Equation 3.17. The exponential component is applied to facilitate comparison by rendering the results as in a more interpretable form. This metric inherently combines the desire for low entropy in conditional label distributions, indicating specificity, and high entropy in the marginal distribution, signifying diversity in the generated images, characteristics desired in the results produced by generative models.

$$\exp(E_x KL(p(y | x) || p(y))) \quad (3.17)$$

The values produced by the equation above need to be higher, which will indicate a more diverse set of high-quality generated images.

3.5.2 Mode Score

The Mode Score (MS) [37] is an improvement on the IS. In simple terms, it measures the dissimilarity between the real and the generated distribution. This makes higher values related to bad results. The expression that characterizes this metric to evaluate the models in question is represented in Equation 3.18.

$$\exp(E_x KL(p(y|x) || p(y)) - KL(p(y) || p(y^*))) \quad (3.18)$$

3.5.3 Fréchet Inception Distance

The Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [38] was proposed as another metric to quantitatively compare generative models. In simple terms, it is calculated by measuring the Fréchet distance, represented in Equation 3.19 between two multivariate Gaussian with mean and co-variance (m, C) and (m_w, C_w) . The first distribution is related to the synthetic images that were generated, and the second is related to the real images that belong to the true dataset. The trace operation Tr in linear algebra computes the sum of elements along the main diagonal of a square matrix. Similar to mean squared (MS) error, higher values of Tr indicate poorer performance of the generative model.

$$\|m - m_w\|_2^2 + \text{Tr}(C + C_w - 2(CC_w)^{1/2}) \quad (3.19)$$

3.5.4 Maximum Mean Discrepancy

The Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) [39] is a statistical measure used to compare two probability distributions $p(x)$ and $q(x)$. It quantifies the difference between these distributions by mapping data into a higher-dimensional space called reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS), where differences can be measured using kernel functions (see Equation 3.20).

$$MMD^2(p, q) = E_{x, x' \sim p}[k(x, x')] + E_{y, y' \sim q}[k(y, y')] - 2E_{x \sim p, y \sim q}[k(x, y)] \quad (3.20)$$

Here, the term $E_{x, x' \sim p}[k(x, x')]$ calculates the expected similarity within the distribution p , measuring how similar samples x and x' drawn from p are according to the kernel function k . Similarly, $E_{y, y' \sim q}[k(y, y')]$ computes the expected similarity within the distribution q , evaluating how similar samples y and y' drawn from q are based on the kernel function k and, finally, $E_{x \sim p, y \sim q}[k(x, y)]$ calculates the expected similarity between samples drawn independently from p and q , according to the kernel function k .

In summary, MMD measures the discrepancy between distributions $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ by comparing their feature means in the RKHS.

3.5.5 Structural Similarity

The Structural Similarity (SSIM) [40] was first introduced in 2004 and it is represented in Equation 3.21.

$$[l(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot [c(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s(x, y)]^\gamma \quad (3.21)$$

This is a metric used to compute the quality of a processed image in comparison to an original or reference image, by quantifying the similarity between the two images, taking into account luminance, contrast, and structure. These three components are represented, respectively, in Equations 3.22, 3.23 and 3.24.

$$l(x, y) = \frac{2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1}{\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1} \quad (3.22)$$

$$c(x, y) = \frac{2\sigma_x\sigma_y + C_2}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2} \quad (3.23)$$

$$s(x, y) = \frac{\sigma_{xy} + C_3}{\sigma_x + \sigma_y + C_3} \quad (3.24)$$

In [40], the authors, in order to simplify the expression of SSIM, decided to set $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$ and $C_3 = \frac{C_2}{2}$). This simplification originates the expression represented in Equation 3.25, which is a specific form of SSIM.

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (3.25)$$

3.5.6 Multi-Scale Structural Similarity

The Multi-Scale Structural Similarity (MS-SSIM) [41] metric represents an enhancement over the SSIM metric, introducing a multi-scale approach to evaluate image details at various resolutions rather than a single one. In simple terms, it takes into account variations in image structures

at different scales as it can be particularly useful for evaluating the quality of images where the observation of details can be important.

The procedure involves taking two images as input (the reference and distorted image) and iteratively applying a low-pass filter and downsampling by a factor of 2. Comparable to SSIM, MS-SSIM considers the luminance (l), contrast (c), and structure (s) of the images. The original image is indexed as scale 1 and the highest scale of the image is indexed as scale M. The luminance component is only computed at scale M, while the contrast and structure components are calculated for every scale of the process. The expression that characterizes MS-SSIM is represented in Equation 3.26, where all the measurements referenced, previously, are combined.

$$[l_M(x, y)]^{\alpha_M} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [c_j(x, y)]^{\beta_j} [s_j(x, y)]^{\gamma_j} \quad (3.26)$$

This metric can provide more flexibility than the single scale approach mentioned before, because it can incorporate variations of image resolution and viewing conditions, essential to simulate subjective evaluation.

3.5.7 Visual Turing Test

The Visual Turing Test (VTT) [42] is a method that generates a series of questions based on a test image, aiming to evaluate the system's capacity to recognize objects and discern characteristics and relationships within images. In the case of generative models, the test is successful if the users being tested are unable to differentiate between images generated and real images.

3.6 Generative Models in Medical Imaging

3.6.1 Generating 2D Images

The study of the generation of medical images through the use of generative models has been growing, in recent years. However, this area of interest is still in its early stages, creating room for improvements and novel research lines and applications.

In [43], Skandarani et al. presented a study about GANs in the generation of medical data, to learn the main advantages and disadvantages of this type of generative model in medical imaging generation. They used the following GAN architectures: Deep Convolutional GAN (DCGAN), Least Squares GAN (LSGAN), Wasserstein GAN (WGAN), HingeGAN, Spatially Adaptive De-normalization GAN (SPADE GAN), and Style GAN. The first four types have the same architecture, which is very similar to the standard framework presented before. The only difference is the substitution of the fully connected layers, that compose the generator and the discriminator, for convolutional layers. Also, between these models, the loss function used to train the discriminator is different. Relatively, to SPADE GAN and Style GAN, these are state-of-the-art models that, with modifications to the standard architecture, generate images with better quality with a more stable training process.

To develop this study, they used three datasets from three different human organs: heart (first row), liver (second row), and retina (third row) [43]. Figure 3.12 shows examples of images generated by each GAN model.

Figure 3.12: Medical Images from each dataset generated by GAN models, from [43].

Skandarani et al. concluded that, despite the images generated being almost impossible to distinguish from the original data - mostly from SPADE GAN and Style GAN -, GANs are not always reliable as a source of medical data, because, most of the time, as it happened in [43], they are developed with the main goal of generating indistinguishable new data without taking into account the 3D characteristics represented in a medical dataset, which has essential information for clinicians.

These ideas motivate the continuous study of generative models with improved frameworks that can create coherent datasets and aid specialists in diverse areas of health.

3.6.2 Generating 3D images

In the context of generating 3D images, in the medical area, GANs are, again, the most explored model from the ones mentioned throughout this document, becoming the state-of-the-art in this field.

In [44], Kwon et al. presented a method for generating realistic 3D brain MRI images using α -GANs [45], which are a type of deep learning model that combine the strengths of VAEs and GANs. In 3D image generation, GANs have an increased probability of producing a limited number of images. To solve this, a VAE is used, since it is immune to this limited production that occurs with GANs. The model proposed uses both generative architectures and an additional code discriminator C - used in α -GAN to replace variational inference -, with all networks presenting adaptations to perform 3-dimensional image generation, such as having 3D convolution layers.

The architecture of this model is represented in Figure 3.13.

Figure 3.13: 3D Auto-Encoding network architecture, from [44].

In this model, C engages in an adversarial contest with the authentic sample encoder, aiming to discern between genuine encoded vectors and those generated from the latent space. The failure of C to successfully distinguish between them signifies the synchronization of the encoder with the latent space.

The discriminator and encoder networks contain five 3D convolution layers, where each one is composed with $4 \times 4 \times 4$ filters. On the other hand, the generator uses conventional nearest neighbor upscale before the convolution layers with $3 \times 3 \times 3$ filters. Finally, the code discriminator network is composed by three fully-connected layers [44].

Relatively to the loss function, the model developed uses the WGAN loss function with gradient penalty (see Section 3.3.2), since using the standard GAN loss was causing more instability in the training process.

The model developed uses a loss function with four parts, one for each part of the network. The discriminator, L_D , which determines if an image is real or fake, is trained on two types of fake images: reconstructed images, $G(z_e)$, and randomly generated ones, $G(z_r)$. Because of this, the loss associated to this block is calculated by adding the distances between these fake images and real images (see Equation 3.27).

$$L_D = E_{z_e} [D(G(z_e))] + E_{z_r} [D(G(z_r))] - 2E_{x_{real}} [D(x_{real})] + \lambda_1 L_{GP-D} \quad (3.27)$$

The networks that analyze the codes used to create the images (code discriminator and encoder) have a similar loss function, L_C , represented in Equation 3.28. The only difference is that, instead of using images, the loss function uses the codes.

$$L_C = E_{z_e} [C(z_e)] - E_{z_r} [C(z_r)] + \lambda_1 L_{GP-C} \quad (3.28)$$

The generator, L_G , which creates images from codes, has a loss function with three parts: the reconstruction loss and two gradient penalty terms, that help reducing the training instability (see Equation 3.29).

$$L_G = -E_{z_e} [D(G(z_e))] - E_{z_r} [D(G(z_r))] + \lambda_2 \|x_{real} - G(z_e)\|_{L1} \quad (3.29)$$

The value used to weight the different loss terms, λ_1 and λ_2 , was 10.

The authors trained the proposed model, which is named 3D α -WGAN-GP, on a dataset of 3D brain MRI images from the Alzheimer’s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) database². They evaluated the generated images using quantitative metrics (see Section 3.5), including multi-scale structural similarity (MS-SSM) and visual inspection. The results, in Figure 3.14, showed that the generated images were of high quality and, sometimes, were mistakenly classified as real.

Although the authors did not present the limitations of their model, it can be interesting to think that, taking into account what was presented in the literature review, the model might have drawbacks inherent to GANs and VAE. Because of this, it was decided that it could be positive to try this model in a dataset of breast MRI images, to verify if it is possible to obtain similar results to the ones obtained in this study. The details about the implementation and training process in the context of this dissertation are presented in Sections 5.1.2 and 5.2.1.

Figure 3.14: 3D Auto-Encoding GAN results (first row) compared to the real samples (second row), from [44].

Another method to generate 3D medical images using GANs was proposed by Sun et al. [46], in 2022, where they developed a Hierarchical Amortized GAN (HA-GAN) that can create high-resolution 3D thorax CT and brain MRI. This model addresses some of the main challenges of GANs for high-resolution medical images generation such as the limited amount of memory required for training and the production of artifacts and inconsistent samples.

In its training phase, it uses a hierarchical architecture, represented in Figure 3.15, composed of two processes that deal with two different structures: a low-resolution version of the entire image and a high-resolution sample of a randomly chosen sub-volume (a smaller section) of the image.

In the generator block, the first branch, represented by the green arrows, processes a random noise vector - $G^A(Z)$ - to create a low-resolution version of a 3D medical image, G^L . Simultaneously, the second branch, represented by the blue arrows, works on the same noise vector, taking the low-resolution image from the first branch as input and increasing its resolution, generating a high-resolution sub-volume, G^H . Both branches are represented by Equations 3.30 and 3.31.

$$\hat{X}^L = G^L(G^A(Z)), \quad (3.30)$$

²ADNI database can be found at <http://adni.loni.usc.edu/>.

Figure 3.15: HA-GAN hierarchical architecture, from [46].

$$\hat{X}_r^H = G^H(S^L(G^A(Z); r)), \quad (3.31)$$

The discriminator block also has a hierarchical structure mirroring the generator. One branch assesses the low-resolution versions of a real image and the image generated by the generator, represented by D^L , while the other branch analyzes the high-resolution sub-volumes from the real data and the generator, represented by D^H . This high-resolution assessment by the discriminator considers the corresponding low-resolution image to ensure that the high-resolution sub-volume preserves the anatomical context.

With this, it is possible to create the two loss functions from each branch, represented by Equations 3.32 and 3.33, that represent the loss function for the high-resolution branch and the loss function for the low-resolution branch, respectively.

$$L_{GAN}^H(G^A, G^H, D^H) = \min_{G^H, G^A} \max_{D^H} E_{r \sim U} [E_{X \sim P_X} [\log D^H(S^H(X^H; r), r)] + E_{Z \sim P_Z} [\log(1 - D^H(\hat{X}_r^H, r))]], \quad (3.32)$$

$$L_{GAN}^L(G^L, G^A, D^L) = \min_{G^L, G^A} \max_{D^L} E_{X \sim P_X} [\log D^L(X^L)] + E_{Z \sim P_Z} [\log(1 - D^L(\tilde{X}^L))], \quad (3.33)$$

In the HA-GAN model, Sun et al. use encoders with a hierarchical structure, defining two types: E^H for high-resolution sub-volumes and E^G for the entire low-resolution volume (see Figure 3.16).

Relatively to the high-resolution encoder loss function (see Equation 3.34), it consists of a single term, that represents the expected value of the absolute difference between the real high-resolution sub-volume $S^H(X^H; r)$ and the generated high-resolution sub-volume $G^H(\hat{A}_r)$.

$$L_{recon}^H(E^H) = \min_{E^H} E_{X \sim P_X, r \in U} [\|S^H(X^H; r) - G^H(\hat{A}_r)\|_1] \quad (3.34)$$

The total reconstruction loss function $L_{recon}^G(E^G)$ (see Equation 3.35) is formulated to train the shared encoder E^G . This block is composed by two main components: the low-resolution and high-resolution reconstruction losses, where the objective is to minimize differences between the generated low-resolution image X^L and the high-resolution sub-volume produced by the generators.

$$L_{recon}^G(E^G) = \min_{E^G} E_{X \sim P_X} [\|X^L - G^L(G^A(\hat{Z}))\|_1 + E_{r \sim U} [\|S^H(X^H; r) - G^H(S^L(G^A(\hat{Z})); r)\|_1]] \quad (3.35)$$

The first term in the equation corresponds to the expected discrepancy between the real low-resolution volume X^L and the generated counterpart $G^L(G^A(\hat{Z}))$. Here, X^L represents the actual low-resolution volume, while $G^A(\hat{Z})$ denotes the output of the common generator block G^A when provided with the latent representation \hat{Z} .

The second term quantifies the expected difference between the real high-resolution sub-volume $S^H(X^H; r)$ and the generated high-resolution sub-volume $G^H(S^L(G^A(\hat{Z})); r)$. In this context, the low-resolution sub-volume $S^L(G^A(\hat{Z}); r)$ serves as the input for generating the high-resolution sub-volume, $G^H(S^L(G^A(\hat{Z})); r)$.

Figure 3.16: Encoder architecture used for the HA-GAN, from [46].

The final model is characterized by the loss function represented in Equation 3.36, where λ_1 and λ_2 balance the contributions of the GAN and reconstruction losses.

$$L = L_{GAN}^H(G^H, G^A, D^H) + L_{GAN}^L(G^L, G^A, D^L) + \lambda_1 L_{recon}^H(E^H) + \lambda_2 L_{recon}^G(E^G), \quad (3.36)$$

Sun et al. trained the proposed model on two different datasets: COPDGene Dataset³, composed of 9276 subjects with 3D thorax CT images, and Genomics Superstruct Project (GSP) Dataset⁴, composed of 3538 subjects with 3D brain MRI images.

HA-GAN was able to produce positive results for both datasets, represented in Figure 3.17, generating sharp images. To confirm this statement, Sun et al. used metrics to quantitatively examine if the synthetic images generated looked realistic, such as Inception Score (IS) (see Section 3.5.1), FID (see Section 3.5.3) and Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) (Section 3.5.4), where higher values for the first metric and lower values for the last two metrics mean that the model can generate higher-quality samples. For the COPDGene Dataset, the average values for IS, FID and MMD were 2.05, 0.005 and 0.038, respectively. For the GSP Dataset, the average values of the same metrics, in the same order, were 1.41, 0.002 and 0.129. These values showed the authors that HA-GAN achieved lower FID and MMD, and higher IS suggesting that this model was able to generate realistic images, when compared with baseline models.

Figure 3.17: Examples of images generated by HA-GAN. In the first row, there are examples of images from COPDGENE Dataset, while on the second row, there are examples of images from GSP Dataset, from [46].

Even though GANs have been present in many studies to generate 3D images, diffusion models are starting to become the main protagonists in this field. In [47], Khader et al. presented a new diffusion model architecture which is composed by a Vector Quantized GAN (VQ-GAN) and the standard architecture of a diffusion model, with modifications to generate 3D samples. Firstly, the

³COPDGene Dataset can be found at <https://www.copdgene.org/>.

⁴GSP Dataset can be found at <https://neuroinformatics.harvard.edu/gsp/>.

training images are encoded into a low-dimensional latent space, which is done by the VQ-GAN. After this step, the diffusion model is trained on this low latent representation of the data. These measures lead the model to use less computational resources, because it samples images using a lower dimensional latent space.

The diffusion model proposed was trained on four public datasets: brain MRI from ADNI⁵, thoracic computed tomographies (CTs) from LIDC⁶, breast MRI from DUKE [48] and knee MRI from MRNet⁷. The model generated realistic 3D images for each dataset with different resolutions, proving its adaptability. The brain MRI images were generated with a resolution of 64^3 voxels, the thoracic CT and breast MRI with a resolution of 128^3 , and the knee MRI with a resolution of $256 \times 256 \times 32$ voxels. In Figure 3.18, each row presents examples of 2D slices of the same volume generated for each type of dataset.

Figure 3.18: 2D slices generated by the model for each dataset used in the training process, from [47].

Also, in order to compare the developed diffusion model with GANs, the authors decided to use Wasserstein GAN. Using the MS-SSIM metric, they observed that the GAN model was not

⁵ADNI database can be found at <http://adni.loni.usc.edu/>.

⁶LIDC dataset can be found at <https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/LIDC-IDRI>.

⁷MRNet dataset can be found at <https://stanfordmlgroup.github.io/competitions/mrnet/>.

able to produce diverse 3D brain samples, because of its high MS-SSIM score, 0.9996. On the other hand, the diffusion model obtained a score of 0.8557, closer to the one obtained by the original data, 0.8095. These results confirmed that the diffusion model used was able to generate realistic and consistent synthetic 3D brain images in a better way than GANs. However, it also presents drawbacks. Besides its, still, large training time, this model is heavily dependent on the compression factor for the latent space, which generates images that do not represent important medical details.

3.7 Summary

In this chapter, four types of generative models were explained in more detail. Autoregressive models can create samples with high quality, however, its training process is characterized by a slow process, since to produce images the model needs to iterate through all samples that compose the image. For large samples, this can be a disadvantageous process. VAEs, on the other hand, offer efficiency in both training and sampling but tend to produce images with noticeable blurriness, compromising realism. GANs are considered the state-of-the-art model in image generation, producing the highest quality results. However, diffusion models have been increasing their reputation in this area, surpassing, even, GANs in synthetic image generation.

Also, this chapter presented the most common evaluation metrics that are essential in assessing image generation models and their outputs. While most of these metrics were created for 2D data it is possible to adapt some to the 3D space.

Finally, in the domain of medical imaging, it was referenced the application of generative models, such as GANs and diffusion models, in synthesizing 2D and 3D medical images. As already mentioned, GANs are the most predominant type of generative model in the studies developed in image generation, since they produce fairly good results. However, in 2D medical image generation, these are not considered reliable, since for most medical applications medical images are used in the 3D representation. Relatively to the latter, GANs produce, also, high-quality samples, but their unstable training environment and lack of diversity in the samples created, have lead researchers to concentrate their attention on diffusion models. This type of generative model, as it happens with GANs, can create high-quality 3D volumes of medical images. Nonetheless, this type of generative model presents drawbacks, such as the usage of large quantities of computational resources and time to train.

Chapter 4

Datasets

To effectively train the models studied in this work, selecting appropriate datasets with a substantial number of 3D medical images was crucial, to ensure that the models have sufficient data to learn from and perform well. Therefore, the Duke Breast Cancer MRI dataset and a private dataset were selected for this study.

4.1 Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI

The Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI dataset [48] is a publicly available collection of breast MRI scans specifically designed for research on breast cancer and it is a valuable resource for researchers developing and evaluating machine learning algorithms.

The breast MRI dataset includes 922 patients diagnosed with invasive breast cancer, collected at Duke Hospital between January 1, 2000, and March 23, 2014, where each patient had a pre-operative MRI available. It contains high-resolution breast MRI scans, featuring various sequences and slices, as shown in Figure 4.1, that provide a detailed view of the breast structure.

Figure 4.1: Example of a breast MRI slice, from Duke breast MRI dataset.

These scans include T1-weighted images, which offer detailed anatomical information and are commonly used to visualize breast structures, T2-weighted images, which help distinguish between different types of tissues and fluids within the breast and dynamic contrast-enhanced (DCE) images, which are taken before and after the injection of a contrast agent, highlighting areas of increased blood flow typically associated with tumors.

Due to availability constraints, this work uses a subset T1-weighted images of the referenced dataset. In this case, 738 T1-weighted images were used, with varying number of 2D slices, as it is demonstrated in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Histogram of the distribution of 2D slices of the 3D images from the subset of the Duke Breast MRI dataset.

4.2 Private Dataset

The BCCT.plan project provided an additional dataset for this study (BCCT.plan — 3D tool for planning breast cancer conservative treatment - NORTE-01-0247-FEDER-017688). This dataset comprises 60 T1-weighted thoracic MRI scans obtained from breast cancer patients using a Philips Ingenia 3.0T MRI scanner, where each scan is composed of a varying number of grayscale axial 2D images in DICOM format, as illustrated in Figure 4.3. These images have a slice thickness of 3 mm and resolutions ranging from 550 to 750 pixels square (0.3–0.5 mm per pixel). Moreover, each MRI scan includes meticulously annotated label masks for anatomical structures present in the images. These annotations were created by domain experts to facilitate precise segmentation and analysis in medical imaging applications.

Figure 4.3: Histogram of the distribution of 2D slices of the 3D images from Private Dataset.

4.3 Pre-Processing

In this study, both referenced datasets were merged together. This decision was made, since both datasets presented a low number of 3D breast MRI images, which could lead to poor results from the models studied. Besides, it was interesting to notice how the models would behave when facing two distributions, potentially generating even more diverse samples.

Relatively to pre-processing, it was designed to handle and prepare the breast MRI images from both datasets, that, initially, are in DICOM format. This is a standardized format for storing, transmitting, and handling medical imaging information, which includes both image data and extensive metadata such as patient information, study details, and image acquisition parameters. However, in this project, this metadata is not used, since the main focus is the actual image, without the concern of representing this data. With this, the images are, firstly, converted from DICOM to PNG, which involves reading the image data, extracting orientation and position metadata, normalizing the pixel values, and resizing the image to the wanted resolution (64^2 or 128^2). This was done, because DICOM files contain medical imaging data along with metadata about the patient, imaging parameters and others, while PNG is a simpler, widely supported image format that stores pixel data without complex metadata, making it easier to handle for applications that only require pixel data, such as image generation.

The number of images available for each 3D breast image is determined and, consequently, the 2D slices are selected. For each one, the necessary vertical flips are applied and, in random cases, a horizontal flip for data augmentation. In Figures 4.2 and 4.3, a varying number of 2D slices for

each sample is possible to observe. Because of this, for 64^3 resolution, if the number of images was less than the required number, the last image would be duplicated until the desired number was reached. If there were more images than needed, only the middle section of the volumes was used. For 128^3 resolution, all selected slices from the previous approach are duplicated. The processed images are then stacked and normalized to a range of $[-1, 1]$, since it helps in stabilizing and speeding up the training process of neural networks. An example of a full pre-processed slice from a 3D breast MRI image is shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Example of a pre-processed slice of a 3D MRI image. In this example, the original image (left) was resized from 512×512 resolution to 64×64 (right). Also, it suffered vertical and horizontal flips and its pixels were normalized to a range of $[-1, 1]$.

4.4 Summary

To train the models in this work, two datasets were selected: the Duke-Breast-Cancer MRI dataset and a private dataset from the BCCT.plan project.

Both datasets were merged due to the low number of 3D breast MRI images, aiming to improve model performance and observe model behavior with different distributions. Pre-processing involved converting DICOM images to PNG, normalizing pixel values, resizing images, and applying data augmentation techniques. Also, the images were stacked and normalized to a range of $[-1, 1]$, with necessary flips applied and duplication or reduction of slices to meet the required number.

However, the usage of both these datasets can be insufficient for this study, because the reduced number of samples available presents one of the main limitations of our study.

Chapter 5

Implementation and Results

This chapter introduces the implementations executed to synthesize 3D breast MRI images. Firstly, it presents the work implemented for the generation of images with 64^3 resolution and, afterwards, it presents the models used to generate images with 128^3 resolution. For both resolutions, the structure of the models, as well as the details of the training processes are presented. The results are analyzed at the end of each section associated to each resolution.

5.1 Synthesis of Breast MRI with 64^3 Resolution

As discussed in the literature review, the model developed in [44] was considered a starting point for this dissertation, since it was able to generate realistic 3D brain medical images. To assess its effectiveness to generate 3D medical images from other organs, this model was compared to a baseline WGAN-GP model at a resolution of 64^3 , evaluating both image quality and the reduction of mode collapse.

5.1.1 3D WGAN-GP

One of the models used was the 3D WGAN-GP original implementation [29]. The changes came in the replacement of 2D convolutions by 3D convolutions and the addition of another dimension, in order to generate 3D images spatially coherent.

The training procedure for this WGAN model involves a systematic sequence of steps aimed at optimizing both the discriminator and the generator, as already demonstrated in Section 3.3.2. As a setup for the training process, the batch size was set to 4, the maximum number of iterations to 200k and the learning rate to 0.0002 for both networks. The parameters for the WGAN-GP loss function were set to 10, as used by the authors in [44], and the latent dimension size was set to 1,000, defining the noise vector fed into the generator to create the synthetic 3D breast MRI images (see Table 5.1). For faster computation, it was used GPU NVIDIA A100.

With the previous setup, the training loop is initiated, iterating up to 200k iterations. In each iteration, the discriminator is, firstly, trained, enabling gradient computation for its parameters and obtaining a batch of real images. These images are passed through the discriminator to get

Table 5.1: Hyperparameters for 3D WGAN-GP.

Hyperparameter	Values
Generator Learning Rate	0.0002
Discriminator Learning Rate	0.0002
Batch size	4
Optimizer	Adam
Iterations	200,000
Latent Dimension size	1,000

predictions and, simultaneously, fake images are generated by the generator with random noise, which are also passed through the discriminator to get predictions. After this, the generator is trained while keeping the discriminator’s parameters fixed.

In Figure 5.1, it is possible to observe an example of a breast MRI, where its slices from 5 to 60 are represented. Despite the relatively low resolution, the slices exhibit reasonable clarity, with the major anatomical structures discernible and clear boundaries between different tissue types. Also, the anatomical structures are coherent across slices, with smooth transitions between consecutive images, ensuring that a 3D volume reconstructed from these 2D slices would be accurate. However, it is possible to notice the presence of blurriness which occurs in a large quantity of samples, when using this generative model.

5.1.2 3D α -WGAN-GP

The 3D α -WGAN-GP used was based on the implementation by Kwon et al. [44] and it uses α -GAN with the WGAN-GP loss.

To train the 3D α -WGAN-GP, the process involves the alternating training of the generator, discriminator, code discriminator, and encoder networks to ensure the effective generation and evaluation of high-quality 3D data. As the setup for the process, the batch size was set to 4, the learning rate to 0.0002 for all networks and the GPU used was GPU NVIDIA A100. The parameters for the WGAN-GP loss function were set to 10, as well as the previous model and the latent dimension size of the noise used to generate the 3D images was set to 1,000 (see Table 5.1).

Table 5.2: Hyperparameters for 3D α -WGAN-GP.

Hyperparameter	Values
Generator Learning Rate	0.0002
Discriminator Learning Rate	0.0002
Code Discriminator Learning Rate	0.0002
Encoder Learning Rate	0.0002
Batch size	4
Optimizer	Adam
Iterations	200000
Latent Dimension size	1000

Figure 5.1: Example of a sample with 64^3 resolution generated by 3D WGAN-GP.

The training loop is initiated, iterating up to the specified total number of iterations, 200k. In each iteration, the generator and encoder are trained together, where the encoder maps real images to latent space and the generator reconstructs these images. Additionally, noise is fed into the generator to produce fake images. The discriminator is then trained independently to distinguish between real 3D samples and those generated by the generator from both latent space encodings and random noise. The code discriminator, which evaluates the latent encodings, is trained to differentiate between encodings from the encoder and random noise.

In Figure 5.2, it is possible to observe an example of a breast MRI generated by this model, where its slices from 5 to 60 are represented. These are more realistic, with well-defined anatomical structures, minimal noise and no significant artifacts, showing significant improvement in clarity and sharpness over the WGAN-generated images. Also, the consistency and smooth transitions between slices ensure accurate 3D reconstruction.

5.1.3 Results

In the 3D space, there is a lack of actual metrics to evaluate synthesized samples created by generative models and quantitatively analyze them, making them not as reliable as their application

Figure 5.2: Example of a sample with 64^3 resolution generated by 3D α -WGAN-GP.

in 2D. However, with the correct adaptations, it is possible to use a certain amount to observe the quality of the images generated and the diversity that the generative models in question can achieve.

In this study, the metrics used to evaluate the realism of the images were FID (see Section 3.5.3) and MMD (see Section 3.5.4). The scores of these metrics were calculated with the average from 100 real-generated sample pairs, for every studied model. To evaluate the diversity, it was used the MS-SSIM metric (see Section 3.5.6). For this metric, the score was calculated with the average from 100 artificially generated or real sample pairs, for every studied model. The values of these metrics for each model and for the dataset are presented in Table 5.3, where it is possible to get a comprehensive quantitative evaluation.

Table 5.3: Comparison of FID, MMD, and MSSIM scores.

Models	FID ↓	MMD ↓	MS-SSIM ↓
3D-WGAN-GP	187.216	28560.824	0.5223
3D α-WGAN-GP	172.878	26437.428	0.4838
Real	-	-	0.40213

A cautious analysis of the values in the table demonstrates that the model 3D α -WGAN-GP outperforms 3D WGAN-GP, as expected. The first one achieved a lower FID and MMD, which

suggests that it was able to match the distribution of the target domain when compared with the second architecture, which obtained values for FID and MMD of 187.216 and 28560.824, respectively. In other words, it is possible to conclude from the quantitative results and the observation of the examples of samples above, that 3D α -WGAN-GP contains a strong ability to match the distribution of the target dataset, for 64^3 resolution, being able to synthesize breast MRI that can achieve some detail, contrast and quality that is present in the real images that belong to the dataset used to train the model.

In terms of diversity, the dataset used presented a MS-SSIM value of 0.40213. Even though 3D α -WGAN-GP has a value not so close to the real dataset, the model 3D WGAN-GP presented a higher value, far from the real one. With this, it is possible to claim that 3D α -WGAN-GP can generate more diversified samples than 3D WGAN-GP.

These results confirm the idea that the model 3D α -WGAN-GP is able to reduce the effect of both blurriness and mode collapse, which are two of the main obstacles in the study and training of GANs.

5.2 Synthesis of Breast MRI with 128^3 Resolution

High-resolution images are crucial for medical analysis. However, GAN training occurs at lower resolutions due to memory limitations and extended training times.

Therefore, in this section of the work, the utilization of HA-GAN [46] was explored, which according to Sun et al., it offers the potential to generate high-resolution images (128^3) without introducing artifacts and with manageable training times. The performance of all three models (3D α -WGAN-GP, 3D WGAN-GP, and HA-GAN) was evaluated at the mentioned resolution using three established metrics: FID, MMD, and MS-SSIM. For the high-resolution images generated by HA-GAN, a Visual Turing Test was considered to further evaluate the similarity between real and generated MRI images. Finally, with the contribution of a super-resolution model developed by a colleague from the same project, we were able to enhance the resolution of some synthesized breast MRI from the HA-GAN model (from 128^3 to 512^3).

5.2.1 3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP

3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP were used in this section to observe the capacities of these models in the generation of 3D breast MRI with higher resolution, in this case 128^3 . Since these models, originally, were developed to generate images with 64^3 resolution, it was imperative to add an additional layer, so they could adapt for a higher resolution.

Aside from this modification, the original training structure and process of the models were preserved, where the established processes for training these GANs were followed meticulously, as well as the preservation of all hyperparameters referenced in Tables 5.1 and 5.2, for 3D-WGAN and 3D α -WGAN-GP, respectively. The consistency in the training regime was critical to ensure that the models would perform reliably and effectively, with the robust foundations already established by the original versions of the models used. This approach was used to facilitate a

direct comparison between the modified and unmodified versions, highlighting the impact of the additional layer on the performance and output quality of the GANs. Also, it allowed to extend the capabilities of 3D-WGAN and 3D α -WGAN-GP to meet the demands of high-resolution 3D medical image generation.

In Figures 5.3 and 5.4, it is possible to observe examples of synthesized breast MRI from 3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP, with 128^3 resolution. As predicted, it is possible to note the presence of some unwanted artifacts (slice 72 in Figure 5.3) and blurriness (slice 96 in Figure 5.4), due to the lower efficacy of these models to generate samples with higher resolution.

Figure 5.3: Example of a sample with 128^3 resolution generated by 3D WGAN-GP.

Figure 5.4: Example of a sample with 128^3 resolution generated by 3D α -WGAN-GP.

5.2.2 HA-GAN

The HA-GAN used was based on the model implemented by Sun et al. [46], which incorporates a hierarchical structure that executes two tasks concurrently, as already mentioned previously.

Firstly, it generates a low-resolution version of the complete image, allowing the model to grasp its overall image structure and intricate anatomical relationships. Also, processing the low-resolution image keeps the memory demands manageable and allows the model to learn these crucial aspects without overwhelming the capacity of the GPU. Secondly, HA-GAN focuses on generating high-fidelity reconstructions, but for meticulously chosen sub-volumes, which is a localized section of the entire image. This enables the model to train on the intricate details present in high-resolution data while ensuring that the memory footprint remains within acceptable limits. By strategically selecting these sub-volumes throughout the training process, HA-GAN exposes itself to the high-resolution intricacies of various image regions.

In this study, the HA-GAN model was trained during 80k iterations (as used originally), where

the process involved the alternating training of the generator, discriminator and encoder networks. The training setup was the same that was used by Sun et al. and it involves setting the learning rates for the generator and encoder at 0.0001 and for the discriminator at 0.0004. The Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) optimizer parameters are configured with $\beta_1 = 0$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$ and the size of the low-resolution image and high-resolution sub-volumes are defined as 64^3 and 16×128^2 , respectively. Also, the feature maps A consist of 64 channels, each with a size of 64^3 . Finally, the latent space of the noise used by the generator has a dimension of 1,024 and the trade-off hyperparameters λ_1 and λ_2 are both set to 5. The referenced hyperparameters are all represented in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4: Hyperparameters for HA-GAN.

Hyperparameter	Values
Generator Learning Rate	0.0001
Discriminator Learning Rate	0.0004
Encoder Learning Rate	0.0001
Batch size	4
Optimizer	Adam
Iterations	80000
Latent Dimension size	1024

In Figure 5.5, it is possible to observe an example of a synthesized breast MRI from HA-GAN, with 128^3 . As it is possible to observe, the 2D slices that compose this volume present smoother transitions between the structures present in the MRI and reveal a better level of sharpness. However, it is possible to note that some details are missing in some slices.

5.2.3 Results

In terms of quantitative results, the metrics used to evaluate the realism of the images were FID (see Section 3.5.3) and MMD (see Section 3.5.4). To evaluate the diversity, it was used the MS-SSIM metric (see Section 3.5.6), similar to the generation of images with resolution 64^3 . The values of these metrics for each model are presented in Table 5.5, where it is possible to get a comprehensive quantitative evaluation.

Table 5.5: Comparison of FID, MMD, and MS-SSIM scores.

Models	FID ↓	MMD ↓	MSSIM ↓
3D WGAN-GP	211.900	220148.84	0.3993
3D α-WGAN-GP	166.608	201911.36	0.4764
HA-GAN	189.724	200879.92	0.4136
Real	-	-	0.3893

As already seen, the FID score measures the distance between the feature vectors of real and generated images, with lower scores representing better image quality and closer resemblance to real images. In this comparison, the 3D α -WGAN-GP model achieved the lowest FID score,

Figure 5.5: Example of a sample with 128^3 resolution generated by HA-GAN.

indicating it produced the most realistic images among the three models. The HA-GAN model also performed well, with a FID score of 190.603, while the 3D WGAN-GP model had the highest score, suggesting it generated images with the least resemblance to real images among the models tested. In terms of the MMD metric, which evaluates the difference in distribution between the real and generated images, the HA-GAN model achieved the lowest MMD score, closely followed by the 3D α -WGAN-GP model. On the other hand, 3D WGAN-GP obtained the highest MMD score, indicating the largest discrepancy between the generated and real image distributions, as predicted. These results highlight HA-GAN's and 3D α -WGAN-GP's superior ability to match the distribution of real images compared to 3D WGAN-GP.

In terms of diversity, the MS-SSIM metric assesses the structural similarity between generated images, with higher MS-SSIM values indicating better structural similarity. The real dataset had an MSSIM value of 0.3893, which serves as a reference point for evaluating the models. The 3D α -WGAN-GP model achieved the highest MS-SSIM score, suggesting it generated images with

close structural similarity, indicating that there is a lack of variety in the synthesized breast MRI. The HA-GAN model followed with an MS-SSIM score of 0.4136, and the 3D WGAN-GP model had the lowest score, indicating, theoretically, that it achieved the best result. However, this value for this last model can be explained by the fact that there are generated examples from this model that are very affected by the presence of unwanted artifacts and blur. This turns the synthesized 2D slices into unrealistic samples, which can make the MS-SSIM lower.

In summary, having into account the previous analysis, the HA-GAN model demonstrated the best overall performance across all evaluation metrics, generating images that are the most realistic and structurally similar to real images. Nonetheless, the 3D α -WGAN-GP model also performed well, particularly in matching the distribution of real images, as evidenced by its MMD and FID scores. This result evidenced one of the conclusions presented in [46]. For 128^3 resolution, HA-GAN outperforms the 3D α -WGAN-GP by a small margin. Because of this it could be interesting to generate, as future work, breast MRI with 256^3 resolution, where the differences may become more evident.

In Figure 5.6, it is possible to analyse the differences between a real slice from a sample of the dataset and a slice from a sample synthesized by the HA-GAN model, both at a resolution of 128^2 . As shown, the generated slice does not contain a good level of detail in the lower area, when compared with the real slice. However, the superior part contains a good level of detail. Because of this, at this resolution, it was hypothesized that the generated image is sufficiently realistic that it could be mistaken for a real MRI slice, even by specialists, due to the reduced ability to discern fine details. So, to evaluate the effectiveness of the HA-GAN model, a Visual Turing Test with a radiologist was decided to be conducted to determine if these generated samples can, indeed, be mistaken for real ones. This test would help assess the practical utility of the HA-GAN model in medical imaging and its potential for clinical applications.

(a) Slice from a real breast MRI

(b) Slice from a HA-GAN generated breast MRI

Figure 5.6: Example of slice 46 from a real, (a), and HA-GAN generated, (b), sample with 128^3 resolution.

5.3 Visual Turing Test

The Visual Turing Test (VTT) was performed by asking a radiologist to evaluate unique breast MRI as real or generated. The test set consisted of real and synthesized MRIs by the model considered as the best in this study, which was HA-GAN. The real scans were randomly selected from the pre-processed dataset and downsampled to 128^3 to match the synthesized examples, while the generated samples were manually selected from the HA-GAN model. This classification performed by the radiologist was based solely on its visual assessment, first impression and experience and it was divided in three sets of images.

In the first set, there were 30 real images and 30 generated images. In the second set, there were 15 real images and 31 generated images. This set introduced a higher proportion of generated images compared to real ones, challenging the radiologist to maintain an objective classification even when the likelihood of encountering a fake image was higher. In the third set, there were 30 real images and 16 generated images. This set reversed the ratio seen in the second set, with more real images than generated ones, testing the radiologist’s ability to identify fake images when they were less prevalent.

It was only chosen images from the middle section of the available breast MRI, since this location has the most amount of information that the radiologist can use to justify the decision made. For the calculations of the confusion matrices, the real scans were considered as negative and the generated as positive (see Tables 5.6, 5.8 and 5.9). Besides, the matrices were then used to calculate 5 metrics (see Table 5.7): accuracy, precision, recall, false omission rate (FOR) and negative predicted value (NPV).

It is important to acknowledge the inherent difficulty radiologists face when classifying images with a resolution of 128^2 pixels. This low resolution results in images with poor detail, making them less informative and more challenging to evaluate accurately, even if they belong to a real dataset. Due to the limited resolution, the decisions made by the radiologist were often based on first impressions, experience and major characteristics of the breast MRIs, rather than on fine details. This limitation can significantly impact the accuracy of classifications, as subtle features that might aid in distinguishing real from fake images are not easily discernible at this resolution.

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Actual	Positive	TP = 22	FN = 8
	Negative	FP = 9	TN = 21

Table 5.6: Confusion Matrix of set 1.

Table 5.7: VTT evaluation metrics.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	FOR	NPV
Radiologist	0.7167	0.7097	0.7333	0.2759	0.7241

The ideal results for this VTT would consist of an accuracy of 0.5, precision of 0, a recall of 0, a FOR of 0.5 and an NPV of 0.5. This would mean that predictions would only be negative and conclude that the generated samples could be mistaken by real samples. By observing the results (see Table 5.7), the radiologist achieved an accuracy of 0.7167. Accuracy represents the overall correctness of the classification and is calculated as the ratio of correctly classified images (both true positives and true negatives) to the total number of images. It indicates that the radiologist correctly classified approximately 71.67% of all images, regardless of whether they were generated or real. In terms of precision, also known as positive predictive value, it measures the proportion of correctly identified positive samples (true positives) out of all samples that were classified as positive. In this context, it means that about 70.97% of the images identified by the radiologist as generated were indeed generated. Relatively to the recall, or sensitivity, this metric measures the proportion of actual positive samples (generated images) that were correctly identified by the radiologist. Its value indicates that the radiologist successfully identified 73.33% of all generated images. FOR is the proportion of false negatives among all samples that were classified as negative. In this context, it means that 27.59% of the images identified by the radiologist as real were actually generated. This metric is important, because it highlights the instances where the radiologist failed to identify generated images, mistakenly classifying them as real. Finally, the NPV measures the proportion of correctly identified negative samples (true negatives) out of all samples that were classified as negative. Its value indicates that 72.41% of the images identified by the radiologist as real were indeed real.

The tests using sets 2 and 3 had the main objective to guarantee that the radiologist was classifying the images based on experience and visualization, instead of luck, since in both these sets, the distribution of real and generated samples was different from 50%. The results for these two tests are presented in Tables 5.8 and 5.9.

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Actual	Positive	TP = 17	FN = 14
	Negative	FP = 2	TN = 13

Table 5.8: Confusion Matrix of set 2.

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Actual	Positive	TP = 13	FN = 3
	Negative	FP = 9	TN = 21

Table 5.9: Confusion Matrix of set 3.

To further understand the thinking process, after classification, the radiologist was asked to give details regarding the classifications on some of the samples that were showed.

(a) Slice from a HA-GAN generated breast MRI with unnatural symmetry

(b) Slice from a HA-GAN generated breast MRI with grey homogeneous tone in denser tissue

Figure 5.7: Example of a slice generated by HA-GAN model with characteristics that helped the radiologist in classifying as generated. On (a), there is an image with unnaturally symmetry, which is not visible in real MRIs and, on (b), an image with a grey homogeneous tone in denser tissue instead of white.

Two specific features that indicated that an image was synthetic rather than real were: the grey homogeneous tone in fatty tissue and the excessive symmetry observed in both sides of the breast (see Figure 5.7). In real breast MRI images, areas that are denser typically appear whiter or brighter due to the high-fat content. If a generated image displays these areas with a more grey and homogeneous tone, it could be a sign that the image is synthetic. This discrepancy arises because the model might have not accurately captured the variability and texture found in real dense tissue, which happened with HA-GAN. Additionally, real breast anatomy is generally asymmetric to some degree due to natural biological variations. However, the model, sometimes, produced images with unnaturally symmetric features on both sides of the breast, which is uncommon in real anatomy.

Besides this, the radiologist noted that one crucial characteristic aiding in the correct classification of real slices was the presence of discernible fibroglandular tissue (see Figure 5.8). This specific anatomical feature, which is typically visible in real MRI scans, provided a tangible cue that helped differentiate authentic images from generated ones.

In summary, the radiologist reported that the resolution of the scans made classification challenging, often requiring them to rely on intuition rather than objective analysis, as already mentioned.

5.4 Enhancing generated 3D breast MRI

In this section, it was used a super-resolution model, implemented and studied by a colleague (Pedro Santos Pereira) that worked in the same project, to enhance the resolution of the images

Figure 5.8: Example of a real breast MRI slice with fibroglandular tissue that helped the radiologist classifying as real.

produced by the HA-GAN model. Given that medical imaging typically requires higher resolution for accurate analysis and diagnosis by clinicians, it is crucial to achieve higher resolutions for visualizing finer anatomical structures and making precise clinical assessments. In this case, the main goal was to enhance the images generated by HA-GAN from 128^3 to 512^3 resolution.

To achieve this, it was used Real-Enhanced Super-Resolution GAN (Real-ESRGAN) [49], a state-of-the-art super-resolution model designed to upscale lower-resolution images while preserving essential details and minimizing artifacts. This model is an improved version of the original ESRGAN [50], incorporating various advancements to better handle real-world images with complex degradation. Some key features of Real-ESRGAN include an enhanced generator architecture that uses Residual-in-Residual Dense Blocks (RRDB), which helps to capture finer details and complex textures more effectively than traditional super-resolution models. An example of the application of this super-resolution model in a 2D slice of a breast MRI image generated by HA-GAN is represented in Figure 5.9.

Through observation, it was able to conclude that applying Real-ESRGAN to the breast MRI images generated by HA-GAN brought several advantages. The upscaled image provides a clearer and more detailed view of the breast tissue (see Figure 5.10), where all the edges and textures are better defined, which proves the model can help improve resolution of MRI images, making it easier to identify and assess finer anatomical structures.

5.5 Summary

The implementation of this study focused on synthesizing 3D breast MRI images at two different resolutions and enhancing their quality. Initially, 3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP models were developed to generate images with a resolution of 64^3 . Evaluation metrics such as FID,

Figure 5.9: Example of a slice generated by HA-GAN model (left) and the same slice applied with Real-ESRGAN (right).

Figure 5.10: Right side in evidence from the same example of a sample generated by HA-GAN model (left) and the same slice applied with Real-ESRGAN (right).

MMD, and MSSIM indicated that the 3D α -WGAN-GP outperformed the 3D WGAN-GP, generating more realistic and diverse images.

For higher resolution images, 128^3 , HA-GAN was utilized due to its hierarchical structure,

allowing for artifact and blur-free high-resolution generation. This model demonstrated superior performance in generating realistic images as measured by FID, MMD, and MSSIM metrics, when compared with 3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP.

In the Visual Turing Test (VTT) with a radiologist, classifying breast MRI images as real or generated proved challenging due to the low resolution. The radiologist relied on intuition over objective analysis, especially given the limited detail of the images. Test sets with varied proportions of real and generated images evaluated the radiologist's ability to discern synthetic characteristics like homogeneous tissue tones and unnatural symmetry, alongside identifying real anatomical features such as fibroglandular tissue. These insights emphasize the complexities in visually assessing synthetic medical images and highlighted the need for improved models that are able to generate the details that were used by the radiologist to classify the synthesized images as fake.

To further enhance the resolution from 128^2 to 512^2 , so that clinicians can analyse in a better way, Real-ESRGAN was applied to the images generated by HA-GAN. This first model preserved essential details and minimized artifacts, resulting in clearer and more detailed images crucial for medical diagnostics, providing better anatomical detail.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter summarizes the findings from the implemented work, where the primary objective was to implement and evaluate generative models for generating high-quality 3D breast MRI images at different resolutions. Also, it provides suggestions for possible improvements that can be implemented in the future.

6.1 Conclusions

The main objective of this work was to develop and study models to synthesise 3D breast MRI images with resolutions of 64^3 and 128^3 with realistic and spatially coherent characteristics. For this we studied the breast anatomy and cancer, as well as the technology behind the MRI imaging technique. Also, it was done research on the literature of generative models.

For the 64^3 resolution, a comparative analysis between 3D WGAN-GP and 3D α -WGAN-GP was conducted, where the second outperformed the baseline model in both image quality and diversity. Specifically, the 3D α -WGAN-GP model achieved lower FID and MMD scores, indicating a better match to the distribution of real images and higher image realism. Additionally, it exhibited reduced blurriness and mode collapse, common challenges in GAN training. The MS-SSIM scores suggested that 3D α -WGAN-GP generated more diverse samples than the 3D WGAN-GP.

For the higher resolution image synthesis at 128^3 , the performance of 3D WGAN-GP, 3D α -WGAN-GP, and HA-GAN was evaluated. The HA-GAN model showed the best overall performance, generating the most realistic images with the closest resemblance to real breast MRI scans, as indicated by the low FID and MMD scores among the models, and maintained good structural similarity and diversity in the generated samples, as reflected in its MS-SSIM score. The comparison illustrated that while 3D α -WGAN-GP still performed well at higher resolutions, the hierarchical approach allowed HA-GAN to handle the increased complexity and detail of 128^3 images more effectively.

A Visual Turing Test (VTT) was conducted to evaluate the perceptual realism of HA-GAN generated images, where a radiologist assessed a set of real and generated breast MRI images,

aiming to distinguish between them. This test was important to understand the main characteristics that turned the images, generated by the HA-GAN model, more unrealistic when compared with real images.

Finally, a super-resolution technique using Real-ESRGAN was applied to enhance the resolution of 3D breast MRI images generated by HA-GAN from 128^3 to 512^3 . This super-resolution model significantly improved the clarity and detail of the synthetic breast MRIs, revealing clearer edges and better-defined textures in the breast tissue.

In conclusion, this dissertation demonstrated the potential of using advanced generative models for synthesizing high-quality 3D breast MRI images. With this, significant progress has been made. However, there remains substantial scope for further research and development to fully realize the potential of these technologies in clinical practice.

6.2 Future Work

The findings of this study open several avenues for future research and improvement, as mentioned previously. Further tuning of the hyperparameters for each model could lead to improvements in image quality and training efficiency, using techniques such as Bayesian optimization or grid search. Besides this, training the models on larger and more varied datasets could enhance their ability to generalize and produce higher quality images. Also, developing and utilizing more advanced and specific evaluation metrics for 3D medical image synthesis would provide a more comprehensive assessment of model performance. Lastly, having completed this study with GANs, the next step involves exploring diffusion models for generating 3D breast MRI images, such as the model developed in [47]. It can be interesting to understand the level of detail that this type of generative models can obtain and if the characteristics focused by the radiologist can be addressed and generate with high level of detail.

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Appendix A

Annexes

Figure A.1: Images generated by a StyleGAN using mixing regularisation, from [30].